

Pesticides and Soil Environment: An Age-Linked Concept

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Abstract

Pesticide was considered complex substances intended for preventing, destroying, or controlling any pest including vectors of human or animal diseases. They are specific chemicals, which contain both “active” or energetic and “inactive” or inert ingredients. The term pesticide includes herbicide, insecticide, nematocide, sanitizer, bactericide, insect repellent, animal repellent, antimicrobial, fungicide, disinfectant, molluscicide, and avicide among others. They are classified based on the mode of entry, mode of function and action, and their chemical composition. These pesticides played a key role in controlling and mitigating variety of agricultural pest and diseases in farm, garden. They contrary, affect soil functional service and great biological biodiversity including human and his environment. Many factors and processes are involved in the transfer, transport and degradation or biochemical conversation of pesticides in soil. The soil factors are the soil organic matter, soil pH, temperature, nutrients, moisture, infiltration rate, aerobic and anaerobic, soil texture and structure. The combined processes are physical, biological, and chemical with great conversion on weathering, hydrolysis, oxidation-reduction, photolysis humification, cheluviation, organic sorting, translocation, *eluviations*, *illuviation*, calcification, podsolisation, gleying, and leaching. Seven important subjects have been treated in a synopsis manner – major groups of pesticides, pesticide toxicity (acute and chronic effects), processes affecting pesticides in soil, pesticides and its ecological effects (soil, crop, biota and human), step by step procedure and soil sampling, techniques involving analysis of pesticides residues in soil, and bioremediation and biodegradation approaches.

Keywords: pesticides: groups, processes, effects, techniques and bioremediation

Introduction

Sustainable agriculture means ensuring food security and better livelihood in rural and urban areas, and this depends on the broad diversity of unnaturally produced chemicals, including pesticides, inorganic fertilizers, and bio-chemicals (Cooper and Dobson, 2007; FAO-WHO, 2014; European Union, 2021). The word pesticide comes from two terms namely ‘pest’ and ‘cide’. Pest is a name used to define any plant or animal or soil organism which is

detrimental or harmful to soil productivity, agronomic plant growth, pastures, forest shrubs and fishes (Usman, 2020). On the other hand, the term 'cide' is a Latin word that means 'to kill' or 'to destroy' (Usman, 2020). Hence, the term 'pesticide' can be considered as a complex name that includes all chemicals used to kill or control pests either in agricultural field or in other environments such as store rooms, human houses and gardens. According to FAO (2002) pesticide can be defined as any substance or mixture of substances intended for preventing, destroying, or controlling any pest including vectors of human or animal diseases, unwanted species of plants or animals causing harm during, or otherwise interfering with, the production, processing, storage, or marketing of food, agricultural commodities, wood and wood products, or animal feedstuffs, or which may be administered to animals for the control of insects, arachnids or other pests in or on their bodies. It may also be regarded as a chemical or biological agent that deters, incapacitates, kills, or otherwise discourages pests in agriculture; and the target pests may include insects, plants pathogens, weeds, mollusks, birds, mammals, fish, nematodes (round worms) and microbes that destroy property, cause nuisance or spread diseases, or disease vectors (FAO, 2002). Kortekamp (2011) also viewed pesticides as any substance or mixture of substances intended for controlling pest and diseases in crop production.

Twenty-seven years ago (1995 to date), the global pesticide consumption is believed to have reached 2.6 million metric tons of active or energetic ingredients; however, this consumption of pesticide has now (2023) reached 3.53 million metric tons (BRC, 2023). The global commercial market of the active pesticide chemicals, also reached \$90.5 billion in 2022 and attained an increased 8.8% (\$98.42 billion) in 2023 (BRC, 2023). Majority of these pesticide chemicals, are marketed illegally. According to the Transnational Alliance to Combat Illicit Trade in agrichemicals and pesticides (TRACIT, 2019), illegal pesticides commercially marketing globally, can be considered as outdated and unauthorized pesticides, pesticides without appropriate regulations, pesticides without tests and licenses, fake pesticide products, un-labelled and fake-labelled pesticide products, and refilled pesticide containers and packages found anywhere in the world.

The major criminal enterprise regarding illicit pesticides marketing in Africa is serious and alarming (Medina-Pastor and Triacchini, 2020; United Nations, 2020). Typically, a global operation called Silver Axe was reported to have seized 1346 tons of illicit pesticides, which were estimated to worth up to €94 million (equal to NGN56400000000), during just the first four months of 2020 (Europol, 2020).

Existing knowledge indicates that the agricultural use of pesticide chemicals contributes greatly to global ecosystem contamination (FAO-WHO, 2018, 2019; Sharma et al., 2019; Bonvoisin et al., 2020; Brescia, 2020; Lin et al., 2022; Geissen et al., 2022). With an increased pesticide use, questions are rising on potential effects regarding public health, soil and water contamination and environmental ecosystem (United Nations, 2018; FAO-WHO, 2020; Braga et al., 2020). This has led to an extensive review of the global pesticide legislation and the scale of challenge in reaching the global harmonization of food safety standards, which highlighted the presence and future consequences of pesticides to global ecosystem and human resources (Möhring et al., 2020). Thus, selection of pesticides to reduce human and environmental health risks was highly recommended in agriculture (Jepson et al., 2020). And, pesticide management approach towards protecting the safety and health of

farmers is binding (Mohammad et al., 2018). Similarly, assessing the farmers' safety and protective behaviour to use pesticides in the farms, was also looked to be necessary (Moradhaseli et al., 2017).

The risk assessment of pesticide molecules is surface soil, water components and plant biomass including animal feeding on the plant biomass has been also demanded in many calls (Ngolo et al., 2019). Mapping the impact of pesticides trading is equally important (Tsimbiri et al., 2015; FAO-WHO, 2014; European Union, 2017; United Nations, 2020). This paper focused on background concept of pesticides in soil, and addressed the following subject areas: major groups of pesticides, processes and factors affecting pesticides in soil and microbial degradation, effects on soil organisms, crop damage and human health, techniques involving analysis of pesticides residues in soil, and bioremediation approaches. This overview, demonstrated and addressed the key issues regarding pesticide and its diverse health issues to soil, plant, human and environment. It is believed that the information has relevance to National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC), and National Environmental Standard and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), all based in Nigeria. Likewise, it would undoubtedly serve as relevance materials to both academic and public health centers, globally.

Major groups of pesticides

Pesticides are specific chemicals, which contain both “active” or energetic and “inactive” or inert ingredients. The former is referred to ingredients, which are sparkling and capable of preventing, destroying, repelling or mitigating a pest of plant and human vectors, present in all pesticide products (US-EFA, 2017). They are considered as plant regulators, defoliants, desiccants, or nitrogen stabilizers, and behave very active in soil causing severe consequences to biological organisms (Usman, 2020). These active ingredients are classified as conventional (pure chemicals), antimicrobial (mixtures of substances), and biopesticides (biological pesticide) (US-EFA, 2017). On the other hand, the inactive ingredients are stationary and immobile in soil, useful for product performance and usability, and contain at least one active ingredient and other calculatedly added inactive ingredients (US-EFA, 2017).

According to Drum (1980), pesticides can be grouped based on three classes, namely, function and action, mode of entry and chemical composition. Fishel and Ferrell (2013) noted that pesticides can be classified based on their function on target pest into the following classes, as outlined by Usman (2020).

Table 1. Pesticides class, description and examples (after Usman, 2020)

No.	Pesticide class	Description	Example
1	Insecticides	These are pesticides formulated to kill, damage or alleviate one or more species of insect found to be a problem to crops. Functions include the disruption of the pest nervous system, and damaging their exoskeletons. Kill insects and arthropods.	Aldicarb
2	Fungicides	This class of pesticides produced mainly to kill fungi and other related organisms such as blights, mildews, molds and rusts.	Azoxystrobin
3	Bactericides	These are produced specifically to kill bacteria and acts against any bacteria that are parasite to plant or biological organisms useful to soil productivity.	Copper complexes
4	Herbicides	These groups of pesticides are produced to destroy weeds and other unwanted plants in farms and gardens.	Atrazine
5	Acaricides	These are pesticides that kill mites and other related organisms feeding on plants and animals.	Bifenazate
6	Rodenticides	This group of pesticides is produced to control rodents, mice and other related organisms.	Warfarin
7	Algaecides	These are used to control or kill growth of algae.	Copper sulfate
8	Larvicides	These are used to inhibits the growth of larvae.	Methoprene
9	Desiccants	These act as reagent on plants by drying their tissues.	Boric acid
10	Repellents	This class of pesticides is used to repel pests by its taste or smell in farm and garden.	Methiocarb
11	Ovicides	This class of pesticides is designed to hinders the growth of eggs of insects and mites.	Benzoxazin
12	Virucides	These pesticides are used to control viruses in soil and plant.	Scytovirin
13	Molluscicides	This class of pesticides is used to inhibit or kill mollusc 's i.e. a snail that usually disturbing growth of plants or crops in farm and garden.	Metaldehyde
14	Nematicides	These are mainly formulated to kill soil nematodes that act as parasites of plants in farms and garden.	Aldicarb
15	Avicides	These pesticides are used to kill birds, which attack rice, pearl millet, wheat and sorghum.	Avitrol
16	Lampricides	These are used to target larvae of lampreys, which are jawless fish-like vertebrates in the rivers and oceans.	Trifluoromethyl nitrophenol
17	Piscicides	These pesticides are formulated to act against parasite fishes.	Rotenone
18	Silvicides	These are used to acts against woody vegetation.	Tebuthiuron
19	Termiticides	These are used to kills termites.	Fipronil

According to Yadav and Devi (2017), classification of pesticides based on mode of entry, can be understood as systemic (non-contact absorbed by plant), non-systemic (contact), stomach poisoning and stomach toxicants, fumigants and repellents. The non-contact is absorbed by the plant and soil, the contact enters the body of pests through their epidermis and causes death, the stomach poisoning enters via mouth and causes death, the fumigants enter the body of pests through their tracheal or respiratory system and caused death, and the

repellents served as disturbance agent to pest, and are capable of deterring the pests from the farm (Usman, 2020).

By and large, classification based on chemical composition of a given pesticide is generally the most important way of understanding pesticide behavior in soil and plant (Handford et al., 2015; Usman et al., 2017). Normally, this classification, gives the knowledge about the physical and chemical properties of pesticides, as well as the active ingredients included (Yadav and Devi, 2017). It also, provides the efficacy and extent of pesticides toxicity and the information that is useful in determining the mode of pesticide application, safety measures, and immediate clarification in case of any accident (Usman, 2020). Four groups of pesticides, were reported namely, organochlorine, organophosphates, carbamates, and synthetic pyrethroids pesticides. Thanks to the works of Yadav and Devi (2017) and Usman (2020) who have provided a comprehensive overview of these three groups of pesticides as presented below.

1. Organochlorine pesticides: These pesticides are used in 1940s and 1960s for the control of mosquito and agricultural pests. They are chlorinated hydrocarbons, which refers to organic compounds attached with five or more chlorine atoms (chlorinated aromatic molecules). Examples are DDT, methoxychlor, dieldrin, chlordane, lindane, endosulfan, benzene hexachloride, kepone, mirex, toxaphene and aldrin. These chemicals worked effectively by disrupting the entire nervous system of the insects leading to convulsions, paralysis and death.

2. Organophosphates pesticides: These pesticides are widely used in farms and garden, homes and offices, grazing lands and sport areas. They are the derivatives of phosphoric acid characterised as biodegradable compounds with less soil contamination effects. They worked as stomach, contact and fumigant poisons leading to nerve damage, paralyse and death of an insect. Examples are diazinon, chlorpyrifos, carbophenothion, endosulfan, parathion, glyphosate and malathion. These pesticides are highly toxic to insects but are relatively less toxic to human and domestic animals such as cows, goats, sheep and camels.

3. Carbamates pesticides: These pesticides are derived from carbamic acid primarily to kill insects. The mode of action is shorter compare to that of organophosphate but interfere in the same way in the nervous system of insects and as stomach, contact and fumigant poisons. Examples are carbaryl, carbofuran, propoxur and aminocarb.

4. Synthetic pyrethroids pesticides: These are pesticides with special active ingredients, which can be synthesized by duplicating the structure of natural pyrethrins 'pyrethrum-like'. They are similar to natural pyrethrins that are produced by the flowers of pyrethrums (*Chrysanthemum cinerariaefolium* and *C. coccineum*), but with longer residual effects than natural pyrethrins. They are highly toxic to insects and fish but slightly toxic to mammals and birds, widely considered to be amongst the safest insecticides for use in foods and on grains. Examples are Cypermethrin and Permethrin.

Pesticide toxicity: acute and chronic effects

Toxicity of pesticide, length and magnitude of exposure, has been considered as the key determinants of the degree of harmful impact on soil organisms and human health (Lorenz, 2009). This can be understood in two forms namely acute and chronic toxicity. According to Yadav and Devi (2017) acute toxicity is the ability of a chemical pesticide to

cause harmful effects in human or biological organism within a very short period after inhalation or contact, whereas chronic toxicity is the ability of a chemical pesticide to cause adverse health effects which follows from long-term exposure to a chemical; and this is expressed in terms of lethal dose 50% (LD₅₀) or lethal concentration 50% (LC₅₀). This LD₅₀ is regarded as the single exposure dose of the poison per unit weight of the organism required to kill 50% of the test population, where the population is genetically homogeneous expressed in milligram per kilogram (mg/kg) body weight (Usman, 2020). According to Singh and Mandal (2013) acute effects occurs as a results of accident and misused, which follows due to untaught concept. Pesticide Action Network (PAN, 2012) reported that the major symptoms that occurs from the chronic effect include birth defects, fetus deformity, genetic changes, blood and nerve disorders, endocrine disruption, and reproduction abnormalities. Continuous exposure to chemical pesticide particularly during application without protective clothes may cause chronic illness. This has been the fact that the joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues (JMPR) and the Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Specifications (JMPS) has led to the compilation of broad lists of pesticides which can serve as a guide to the concept of pesticides in the field of agriculture and environment in general. The information may be useful to both academic environment, National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC), and National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) operating in Nigeria.

Processes and factors affecting the transfer and transport of pesticides in soil

The processes that involved in the pesticides communication with soil and biochemical conversion, are complex and dynamics. Usman et al. (2017) considered these as sorption, adsorption, physical and chemical processes, and microbial degradation. According to Usman (2020) as noted from the detailed study of soil formation and soil profile development (Jenney, 2009), numerous processes are involved in the transfer and transport of pesticide molecules in soil and plant. These include the physical, chemical, biological and ecological processes, which are set of mechanisms, considered complex in soil formation (Usman, 2013). It is evident that when pesticide get contact to soil, the following processes play a key role in the potential degradation of pesticides (Ngolo et al., 2019). These soil processes can be understood from the following viewpoints (Waugh, 2000; Usman, 2020):

1. Weathering: This is a breakdown of soil particles by physical, chemical and biological factors. During this process, pesticide molecules can be further broken, and affect the soil materials.

2. Humification: This is a process of decomposition of organic matter into humus. Pesticide molecules attached to the organic materials, can be included into this decomposition and affect the soil particles.

3. Cheluviation: This is the transport of chelates or nutrients and organic acid downwards through the soil profile. Molecules of pesticides are said to be transported into the various parts of soil profile during this process.

4. Organic sorting: This is the reorganization of minerals and organic matter into the horizons. The arrangement may contribute to the great distribution of pesticide molecules in soil voids.

5. Translocation of soil materials: This is the movement of soil components in a form of solution, suspension, biological activities or direction (downward and upward).

Translocation is one of the most serious soil process that moves pesticide molecules easily from one area to another by means of solution, suspension and/ biological agent.

6. Eluviations: This is a process of washing out of materials – the removal of organic and mineral matter from the A-horizon. Pesticide molecules that decompose with organic material during humification, can be washed out to A-horizon.

7. Illuviation: This is a process of in-washing – the re-deposition of organic and mineral matter in B-horizon. Similarly, pesticide molecules that are decomposed along with organic material during humification, can be washed-into B-horizon.

8. Calcification: This is a process of calcium accumulation in B-horizon – occurs where precipitation is equal or slightly high than evapotranspiration (tropical areas). During this accumulation of calcium, molecules of pesticide can be carried away by rainfall to other part of the surface soil.

9. Podsolization: This is the removal of iron and aluminium oxides together with humus – occurs where precipitation is greatly more than evapotranspiration (cool or humid areas). During this removal process, molecules of pesticide can be removed by the rainfall to other parts of the surface soil.

10. Gleying: This occurs when the output of water from the soil system is restricted, giving anaerobic or waterlogged soil conditions. Particles of pesticide can be deposited along with gley materials.

11. Leaching: This is a removal of soluble material in soil solution – occurs where precipitation exceeds evapotranspiration while soil drainage is good. Pesticide molecules can be leached into the soil profile zones, and contaminate the soil.

Soil organic matter, soil pH, temperature, nutrients, moisture, infiltration rate, aerobic and anaerobic, soil texture, and structure, are considered the most common factors affecting and controlling the effectiveness of soil-applied pesticides as well as the bio-chemical degradation in soil (Katagi, 2004). For example, Gold et al. (1996) noted that in the bio-chemical conversion of pesticides, soil pH and clay content are found to affect the persistence of *bifenthrin*, *chlorpyrifos*, *cypermethrine*, *fenvalerate*, *permethrin*, and *isofenphos*. This conversion was noted to be faster in the silt loam soils compared to sandy-loam and sandy soil for soil affected by *imidacloprid* and *diazinon* (Jones and Ananyeva, 2001). The persistence and biodegradation of these two pesticides in soil together with *pencycuron* degraded faster in coastal saline soil than in alluvial soil and soil amended with decomposed cow manure (Hafez and Thiemann, 2003). Racke et al. (1994) noted that herbicides such as atrazine and trifluraline disappeared more rapidly under anaerobic conditions than under aerobic conditions. However, this might be very limited due to the absorption process that prevents the release of pesticides into the soil solution and the loss by causing dislocation during leaching and runoff (Pal et al., 2005).

Pesticide degradation in soil

The term ‘degradation’ as applied to the concept of pesticides in soil means breakdown of pesticide molecules in soil solution. Katagi (2004) considered this breakdown as a process of pesticides dissolving in soils, which results in the conversion of its molecules into simpler compounds such as H₂O, CO₂, and NH₃. Buchel (1983) noted that this breakdown might further be increased as a result of chemical reactions such as solubility, volatilization, adsorption and desorption, hydrolysis, photolysis, microbiological catabolism, and

metabolism; considered the major route of mineralization (Usman, 2020). These sets of processes are controlled by three modes of degradation in soil namely: biological (breakdown by micro-organisms), chemical (breakdown by chemical reactions, such as hydrolysis and redox reactions), and photochemical (breakdown by ultraviolet or visible light). Microbes in soil used pesticides as a food source under biotic and abiotic transformation processes (Gavrilescu, 2005). Usman (2020) noted that the biotic conversion is mediated by microorganisms, while abiotic conversion embroils the processes such as chemical and photochemical reactions. The key factors involved in these two conversions mostly in soil-water conditions, are hydrolysis, oxidation-reduction and photolysis (Burns, 1975). However, hydrolysis and redox-reactions are the main regulators in sediment conditions, with redox reactions mediating in aquatic environments by direct or indirect photolysis (Burns, 1975). Similarly, hydrolysis and redox reactions are considered the major processes controlling the breakdown of pesticides in soil liquid and solid forms (Usman et al., 2017). Soil moisture, temperature, aeration, pH, and organic matter are considered the key components of microbial degradation in soil (Drum, 1980).

According to Usman (2020), surface and sub-surface soil medium are the positions where chemical degradation of pesticides occurs although very high at the surface medium. It has been described that soil temperature, moisture, pH, aeration, light and the ability of pesticide molecules to adhere and adsorb to soil particles, are the major factors enhancing the chemical degradation of pesticides in soil (Drum, 1980; Usman, 2020). Photochemical degradation, on the other hand, is an abiotic process that describes the dissipation of pesticides where molecular excitation by absorption of light energy results in various organic reactions (Katagi, 2004). This form of pesticides degradation in soil is influenced by the intensity and spectrum of sunlight, length of exposure, and the properties of the pesticide molecules (Katagi, 2004).

Pesticides and its ecological effects: soil, crop, biota and human concerned

Pesticides as chemical agent is used for preventing and destroying pest to achieve high crop yield and sustainable food security (Handford et al., 2015). However, these chemicals have more negative impact the key components of the ecosystem: soils, crops, water, forest, biota, and human (Zikankuba et al., 2019; Ndungu et al., 2019; Bonvoisin et al., 2020; Brescia, 2020). The national and international concern about their various effects remains an area of interest (Yao, 2020). Soils, crops, water and the human environment are four components, that must be put into consideration with regard to pesticides and ecological effects. According to Joko et al. (2020) illicit pesticides, are highly toxic and might poison almost all components of human and biological lives including water bodies, soil voids, aquatic organisms and the overall ecosystem. Usman (2018) emphasized that soil quality, plant health, water quality and human health, must be protected from the chronic effects of pesticides. These four subject areas have been regarded as the major target of pesticides when released into the environment for a particular purpose (Lai, 2017; United Nations, 2018; FAO-WHO, 2019). The pesticides molecules released during spraying in the field, immediately come into contact with soil and plant residues (Bollag et al., 1992; Braga, 2020; Lin et al., 2022; Geissen et al., 2022). The soil and its biological components (parent

materials, biota and biodiversity, water), the plant and biomass, and also, the atmosphere and air circulating, are at high risk of becoming contaminated by the synthetic molecules of pesticides (Yao, 2020).

Soil biota play a vital role in soil quality and soil fertility development, and plant growth as well (Usman et al., 2016). The interaction between these biological organisms and pesticides has effects on their biodiversity, and soil-crop health relationship (Usman et al., 2017). Sebiomo et al. (2011) noted pesticides decrease the microbial population and cause significant damage to soil and plants. Pesticides such as butachlor were reported to suppress the microbial population and deter their enzyme activities in soil (Min, et al., 2007; Xia et al., 2012). Other pesticides were observed to have severe effects on crops, and are capable of destroying great number of non-target organisms (Constenla et al., 1990). These severe effects reduce the functional services in soil system, eliminate the biological diversity, and damage plant systems at a very early stage of growth (Sharma et al., 2019). According to Kalia and Gupta (2004), pesticides disrupt the food web and put the entire ecological system at very risk of altering the biosynthetic mechanism, affecting the protein synthesis and cellular membrane, and disorderly plant growth. Study by Mayeetreyee et al. (2013) noted a significant reduction of heterotrophic aerobic bacterial count and fungal population in soil treated with paraquat and glyphosate pesticides. Similarly, a group of herbicides such as butachlor, pyrazosulfuron, paraquat and glyphosate have been observed to cause damage to plant biomass and delay a substantial microbial function on the proper decomposition of organic matter (Bolter et al., 2006). Other studies of recent analyses in this regards include the recovery of selected drugs and herbicides from soil (De Carlo et al., 2015), the analysis of five neonicotinoid insecticides and their primary metabolite in cucumbers and soil (Abdel-Ghany et al., 2017), determination of dioctyl diethylenetriamine acetate residues in soil (Gong et al., 2018), determination of polyoxin b in cucumber and soil (Song et al., 2019), monitoring of 218 pesticide residues in clay loam soil (Acosta-Dacal et al., 2021), Simultaneous multi-residue pesticide analysis in southern Brazilian soil based (Do Amaral et al., 2022), and multi-residue method for trace analysis of pesticides in soils (Rösch et al., 2023).

The synthetic pesticides molecules, play a major role in contaminating environmental ecosystems, and affect many aspects of human health developments as well (Haggblade et al., 2019). They are poisons and can be hazardous when misused in the farm or garden (FAO-WHO, 2019; United Nations, 2020). They poisoned almost all components of the human body including hairs, skin, eyes, sliver, and clothes (Lai, 2017; Joko et al., 2020). Many studies reported different pesticide cases on human and environmental health impact (Khan, 2009; Handford et al., 2015; van Wendel de Joode et al., 2016; Larsen et al., 2017; El-Haoud et al., 2017; Mohammad et al., 2018; Mora et al., 2018; Cappa et al., 2022; Marks-Perreau et al., 2023). The complex environmental and human health effects of pesticides reported by these studies are largely due to the commercialization of the illicit chemicals (European Union, 2021). The toxicity level and formulation of the energetic ingredients contained in these outdated pesticides are produced without test and quantification (United Nations, 2018; TRACIT, 2019). This toxicity of pesticide molecules has detrimental effects on human health (Lorenz, 2009). Diseases such as brains (neuroblastoma) cancers, soft tissue sarcomas, colorectal and testes carcinomas; hormonal imbalances leading to infertility, breast pain, menstrual disturbances, adrenal gland exhaustions and early menopause among others, have

been linked to high level of exposure to toxic pesticides (Larsen et al., 2017; van Wendel de Joode et al., 2020). The common symptoms reported include eyes and skin irritation, body shivering, headaches, body aches, skin rashes, poor concentration, nausea, dizziness, impaired vision, cramps, panic attacks and in severe cases coma and death could probably occur (Mohammad et al., 2018; Joko et al., 2020). The human birth effect, infants and children multiple diseases cases are also noted as a result of pesticide use in agriculture (Larsen et al., 2017; Mora et al., 2018; Widyawati et al., 2020). This has also linked to problems related to inability to speak fluently, hormonal imbalances leading to infertility, breast pain, menstrual disturbances, adrenal gland exhaustions, early menopause, immune system dysfunction leading to immune suppression that cause potentially serious health risks and also subject to malnutrition (Xavier et al., 2004; Tsimbiri et al., 2015). These complex health issues are considerable (WHO, 2017; Zikankuba et al., 2019), and need to be on a regular check and balance assessment particularly in northern Nigeria where many rural farmers are mingling with pesticides on daily times (Usman, 2020).

Techniques involving analysis of pesticides residues in soil

The human relationship with soil is a long-term friendship and has recorded many benefits and detriments as well. The entire soil body represents one of the most complex mediums with diverse functional services and interactions of pesticides that take place through various processes and compound factors (Bollag et al., 1992; Usman and Kundiri, 2016). The use of pesticides in soil has infiltrated the existence of many residues, which are unfriendly to the soil itself, and biological organisms living within (Pelosi et al., 2021; Geissen et al., 2021). The employment of soil-based techniques for the analysis of these pesticide residues in soil has become necessary (Leo et al., 2016; Usman, 2020). This is to provide open access to short- and long-term worldly risk assessment of eco-toxicological effects of pesticides in soil bodies and biological lives including humans and the environmental ecosystem. In this development, many techniques and ideas have been used to achieve this risk assessment. The use of traditional techniques, which employed the application of examples of liquid–liquid extraction, Soxhlet extraction, sonication assisted extraction among others, are laborious, expensive, time-consuming, and require large amounts of organic solvents, which also involve many steps, leading to loss of some analyte quantity, consequences with the use of hydrocarbon solvents such as depletion of the ozone layer, and producing of carcinogenic waste (Mondal, 2020).

However, considering the historical catastrophes of pesticides in creating soil contamination and soil pollution (Usman et al., 2017; Usman, 2018), the scientific advancements, has provided some alternative techniques that are quick, easy, cheap, effective, sharp, and safe to replace previous, less efficient extraction methods for pesticide analysis (Varela-Martínez et al., 2020). These alternative techniques, include the use of solid phase extraction (SPE), solid phase micro-extraction (SPME), supercritical fluid extraction (SFE), microwave assisted extraction (MAE), microwave-assisted micellar extraction (MAME), accelerated solvent extraction (ASE), matrix solid phase dispersion (MSPD) extraction, and QuEChERS (quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged and safe) method (González-Curbelo et al., 2022). These methods have been developed for a purpose of overcoming the shortcomings of the traditional techniques, even though some of them (e.g. SFE, ASE and MAE) are

instrumental techniques, useful for the desired purpose such as purification (SPE) and concentration (SPME) of obtained extracts (Mondal, 2020).

Step by step procedure and soil sampling

The general step by step procedures for the removal of pesticide residues from the soil is believed to begin with an advanced design of the experiment or choosing the best and friendly techniques. This will be followed by sampling, extraction, clean-up and estimation. In this regard, soil samples should be taken using pedon idea as introduced by Soil Survey Staff (2022) or from growing farm using the idea of grid pattern that should consistently be distributed all over the intended farm (Mondal, 2020). For practical interest, Mondal (2020) is suggesting 3×3 grid with nine total sample proportions for smaller fields, 4×4 with sixteen sample proportions for the medium-sized fields, and 5×5 with more than sixteen proportions for larger grids and very large fields. According to him each sample site stands as a reference of one portion of the total sample. This means that soil sample has to be taken at each site with two soil plugs of about 15 cm deep and 3 to 5 cm μ ; whereas the combined two plugs at each site will become a one sample portion (Mondal, 2020).

Examples of some modern techniques of pesticide residues analysis

1. QuEChERS technique: This technique means quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged, and safe (QuEChERS) approach, and was first introduced in 2008 by Lesueur *et al.*, (2008) after publishing their work titled ‘*Comparison of four extraction methods for the analysis of 24 pesticides in soil samples with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and liquid chromatography-ion trap-mass spectrometry*’. Since its known procedure and techniques, the QuEChERS has received the attentions of many studies year after year (Lesueur *et al.*, 2008; Pinto *et al.*, 2009; Rashid *et al.*, 2010; Caldas *et al.*, 2011; Temir *et al.*, 2012; Rouvire *et al.*, 2012; Fernandes *et al.*, 2013; Chai *et al.*, 2014; De Carlo *et al.*, 2015; Zhou *et al.*, 2016; Abdel-Ghany *et al.*, 2017; Gong *et al.*, 2018; Song *et al.*, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2020; Acosta-Dacal *et al.*, 2021; Do Amaral *et al.*, 2022; Rösch *et al.*, 2023). Significant achievement has been made in the analyses of organochlorine, organophosphorus pesticides, pyrethroid pesticides, neonicotinoids], carbamates, triazole, and urea derivatives, with the advanced QuEChERS (Chai *et al.*, 2014; Abdel-Ghany *et al.*, 2017; Ma *et al.*, 2020; Mohamed *et al.*, 2021; Rösch *et al.*, 2023). Many advanced and modified procedures were developed using QuEChERS more especially when analysing different pesticides in soil and plant (Lehotay *et al.*, 2007; Mohamed *et al.*, 2021; Rajput *et al.*, 2021).

2. Multiple Parameter Hazard Assessment Scoring System (MPHASS): Multiple Parameter Hazard Assessment Scoring System (MPHASS) is a technique that employed the ideas of Chemical Scoring System (CSS) introduced by O’Byrne and Ross (1988) as designed by US-EPA office of toxic substances and the Oak Ridge National Laboratory. This technique combines multiple parameters such as human, soil, water, plant and animal components of environmental ecosystem. The soil parameters include the water in soil, soil materials in *illuviation* zone, soil materials in *eluviation* zone, soil materials in rhizosphere zone; soil biota: bacteria, fungi, ant, termites and nematodes.

3. A handheld SRS microscope: A handheld SRS microscope is a direct method, and can be used for pesticide analysis in both soil and plant (Figure 1). The technique is a modern method, and can detect the pesticide residue *in situ*, with high speed, under ambient light, and

without special sample preparations, providing a convenient examination platform with a label-free detection of the pesticide residue (Lin et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Typical handheld SPS microscope in situ detection of pesticide on crop*

* - This image is cited from Lin et al. (2022), and was appeared as: Fig. 37.5. In situ detection of pesticide residues on crop product by a handheld SRS microscope. (A) Digital picture of the experimental setup. (B) SRS image at 1605 cm^{-1} of a spinach leaf. (C) SRS image at 1679 cm^{-1} of a spinach leaf. (D) MCR output spectra. (E, F) SRS concentration maps of chlorophyll and thiabendazole. The image was Reprinted with permission from C.-S. Liao, et al., In vivo and in situ spectroscopic imaging by a handheld stimulated Raman scattering microscope, ACS Photonics 5 (3) (2018) 947–954. Copyright 2021 American Chemical Society).

4. Multi-residue method via QuEChERS techniques: This technique employed the idea of QuEChERS in a multi-purpose manner for the analysis of pesticide residues in soil. Rösch et al. (2023) have accurately quantify 146 currently used pesticides in agricultural soils with varying soil properties using a multi-residue method for trace analysis of pesticides in soils with special emphasis on rigorous quality control. According to Rösch et al. (2023) pesticides were extracted using an QuEChERS technique while chemical analysis was carried out by liquid chromatography attached to tandem mass spectrometry (triple quadrupole). Similarly, quantification was done based on matrix-matched internal standards calibration, using 95 isotopically labeled analyte analogues; the validated was conducted by an in-house prepared partly aged soil, which contains all target pesticides and by agricultural field soils with native pesticide residues (Rösch et al., 2023). They considered their multi-residue technique as highly sensitive, precise and true for regular monitoring of soils contaminated with pesticide residues.

5. Solid Phase Micro-Extraction (SPME) technique: This is one of the newly developed technique widely used for the pesticide residues analysis in soil. The technique is set to run concurrently for purification and concentration of the sample extract. According to Mondal (2020), the SPME syringe is used as the main part of this method that is visually resembling on the chromatographic system contained a 1 cm long fiber which is located within the needle of the syringe. This syringe needle is made of an appropriate polymer

deposited on the holder of fused silica. However, Mondal (2020) noted that the micro-extraction process is fixed based on the rearrangement of extract between micro-extraction fiber and sample matrix which he described as thermal in the case of the gas chromatography or by solvent elution in the case of liquid chromatography.

Conclusions

This evaluation discussed the concept of pesticide in soil with reference to the general concept of pesticide and its major groups, pesticide toxicity (acute and chronic effects), processes affecting pesticides in soil, pesticides and its ecological effects (soil, crop, biota and human), step by step procedure and soil sampling, techniques involving analysis of pesticides residues in soil. An intended study reflecting on pesticides analysis in soil, will be enlighten with the information discussed in this paper. As other similar reviews have confirmed, the content of this paper, is an appraisal towards better understanding of pesticides and how it affects the health condition of soil, plant, and human ecosystem. Analysis of pesticide in soil with modern techniques, is a good step towards better sustainable management of best use of pesticide in farms and garden. This is also vital towards better understanding of the complex effects of pesticides in soil and human environment. Some examples of the ways to be used for sustainable analysis of pesticide residues in soil are provided. These examples can be served as a guide towards better understanding of pesticide residue analysis in soil and plant.

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Author contributions

Suleiman Usman provided general text and organized the detail explanation. James O. Jayeoba improved the text quality and provide updates to it. Sani Mathew Amana improved the introductory concept and aspect of pesticide and its ecological effects. All authors contributed to the general concept of the paper.

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